

VISITOR PERCEPTIONS OF THE IMPACT OF LOCAL FESTIVALS ON REGIONAL TOURISM AND SUSTAINABILITY PROCESSES; A QUALITATIVE RESEARCH IN SILIFKE

Özgür UYSAL (Master Student)

Selcuk University, Faculty of Tourism, ouysal707@gmail.com

Mersin / Türkiye

ORCID: 0009-0007-187-383x

Doç. Dr. Kürşad SAYIN

Selçuk University, Post Vocational School of Silifke, kursadsyn@selcuk.edu.tr

Mersin / Türkiye

ORCID: 0000-0003-0988-5186

Abstract

The aim of this study is to examine the impact of local festivals on tourism development and sustainability based on participant opinions. A qualitative research method was employed, and data was collected from 16 participants through a semi-structured interview form. The findings indicate that, according to participant perceptions, festivals make significant contributions to destination promotion, attracting tourists to their regions, and regional development. The majority of participants stated that festivals are effective in promoting local culture, increasing tourist appeal, and fostering economic activity. However, when evaluated from a sustainability perspective, it was determined that insufficient attention is paid to environmentally friendly practices. Consequently, it is demonstrated that festivals, in addition to their touristic and economic contributions, should be conducted with an awareness of environmental responsibility. The study emphasizes the need for local governments and festival organizers to plan according to sustainability principles. Furthermore, it is recommended that festivals be considered not only as promotional activities but also as tools for sustainable tourism.

Keywords: Festival Tourism, Silifke, Sustainability, Local Festivals

1. Introduction

Festivals are cultural events held to celebrate the cultural values, beliefs, artistic activities, and traditions of a particular community, attracting high levels of community participation (Getz, 2010). Initially established for traditional and religious purposes, festivals have now become significant tourist attractions (Derrett, 2003). Festival tourism refers to tourists participating in local events motivated by their desire for cultural experiences. Such events contribute to the differentiation of destinations, the extension of the tourist season, and the revitalization of the local economy (Arcodia & Whitford, 2006). Furthermore, festivals strengthen regional identity by creating spaces for social interaction for both visitors and locals (Gursoy, Kim, & Uysal, 2004).

Touristic and cultural festivals are considered important tools for promoting destinations, preserving local identity, and supporting regional development (Getz, 2010).

Today, festivals are not only entertainment events but also strategic elements that revitalize regional tourism and promote sustainable development (Derrett, 2003; Richards & Palmer, 2010). Sustainability is one of the key factors determining the long-term success of tourism (Uzal, 2025). In this context, the participation of local people in events, the equitable sharing of economic returns, and the preservation of cultural values emerge as indispensable components of sustainable tourism (Hall, 2008). In this context, understanding the impact of festivals in settlements with tourism potential and their sustainability are crucial for the sustainability of local development policies.

The aim of this research is to examine the impacts of local festivals on tourism and visitor perceptions regarding their sustainability using a qualitative approach. The fact that most studies on festival tourism in Turkey focus on the quantitative and economic dimensions (Çelik, 2019; Girtlioğlu & Avcıkurt, 2010), while qualitative research based on visitor experiences and perceptions remains limited, points to a significant gap in the literature. This research aims to fill this gap by evaluating festivals not only as events but also from a sustainable tourism perspective. Thus, the study offers a unique perspective on the role of local festivals in tourism planning, both theoretically and practically.

Silifke, with its historical and cultural heritage, is a significant tourist attraction in the Mediterranean region. At the "International Music and Folklore Festival" held in the district, yogurt and batirik competitions are held, and local foods and beverages such as sıkma, saç böreği, yahni, batirik, döğme, keşkek, and thyme ayran are served in tents belonging to the Yörük culture. Various local activities held during the festival contribute to both the promotion and economic development of the region (Kaya, 2024). However, academic studies on the impact of these festivals on regional tourism and sustainability are limited. Therefore, the current research aims to examine the impact of the festival held in Silifke on regional tourism and the sustainability processes of the festivals from a qualitative perspective. This study aims to reveal the impact of the festivals on Silifke's tourism dynamics by analyzing the perceptions of local visitors. It is thought that the findings will contribute to the development of sustainable festival tourism policies and will serve as a guide for similar destinations.

2. Literature Review

2.1. The Concept and Importance of Festival Tourism

Festivals are among the most important tourism attractions that highlight a destination's cultural identity and bring together locals and visitors (Getz, 2010). Furthermore, festivals are seen as an important marketing tool for destination branding, promotion, and visitor attraction (Lee, Lee & Wicks, 2004).

Festival tourism refers to tourists' participation in local activities to learn about cultures (Arcodia & Whitford, 2006). Festival tourism activities balance seasonality in small-scale settlements or regions with a short tourist season, while also increasing destination attractiveness (Derrett, 2003). Through these events, tourists have the opportunity to experience local traditions, cuisine, music, and folkloric elements, while also gaining a promotional advantage for the destination (Arcodia & Whitford, 2006). Another important aspect of festival tourism is that it strengthens socio-cultural ties within local communities and contributes to the preservation of region-specific values (Picard & Robinson, 2006). In this respect, festivals are seen not only as economic but also as a tool for cultural sustainability. The temporary tourist activity generated by festivals directly contributes to the local economy through the accommodation, food and beverage, and retail sectors (Janiskee, 1994). However, negative effects such as increasing tourist pressure, environmental pollution, excessive commercialization and identity erosion bring up sustainability discussions in the festival-tourism relationship (Mair & Whitford, 2013).

2.2. Sustainability and Tourism Interaction in Festivals

Sustainability in tourism is a multidimensional concept encompassing socio-cultural, economic, and environmental dimensions (Uzal, 2025). Festivals energize the local economy while also enabling the preservation of local culture and increased social participation (Hall, 2008). However, if these events are not planned in accordance with sustainability principles, environmental pressures and tensions between local residents and tourists can arise (Getz, 2010).

In recent years, the concept of "sustainable festival management" has gained importance. This concept is defined as "planning events that meet the cultural and social needs of today's society without compromising the needs of future generations" (Getz, 2009). Sustainable management of festivals ensures both the preservation of the destination's image and the strengthening of its long-term tourism potential (Kim, Uysal & Chen, 2002). In this context, sustainable festival practices: Reducing environmental impacts requires the participation of local people in decision-making processes, the fair sharing of economic benefits, and the preservation of cultural identity (Laing & Frost, 2010).

In most studies conducted in Turkey, the issue of festival sustainability has not been systematically addressed, but is generally examined indirectly within general tourism policies (Küçükaltan & Pirnar, 2016). This suggests that the sustainability strategies of locally organized festivals have not been adequately analyzed.

3. Materyal And Method

3.1. Importance and Purpose of the Research

Turkey, with its rich cultural heritage and local festivals, has significant potential for festival tourism (Alaeddinoğlu, 2007; Çelik, 2018). However, it has been emphasized that research examining these festivals from a sustainability perspective is limited and that qualitative research, particularly at the local level, is needed in this area (Demir & Kozak, 2019). In this sense, the Silifke example offers an important field of study for the preservation of cultural values, the enhancement of tourist appeal, and sustainable development.

While numerous studies in the international literature focus on the economic contributions of local festivals (Çelik, 2019; Giritlioğlu & Avcıkurt, 2010) and the environmental or economic sustainability of local festivals (Laing & Frost, 2010; Arcodia & Whitford, 2006; Laing & Frost, 2010), studies examining visitors' perceptions of festival sustainability are quite limited. However, visitors are one of the key actors that ensure the continuity of a festival (Andersson & Getz, 2008). Furthermore, most existing studies are based on surveys conducted with festival organizers or local government representatives; visitors' perceptions of festival sustainability are often excluded from the scope of research (Laing & Frost, 2010; Mair & Whitford, 2013). However, visitors are one of the main stakeholders that ensure the continuity of a festival, and their satisfaction levels and perceptions of sustainability directly affect the sustainability and future of the event (Andersson & Getz, 2008; Baker & Crompton, 2000).

Visitor-focused research enables the adoption of a stakeholder approach in festival planning and contributes to the development of sustainability strategies (Andersson & Getz, 2008). Therefore, understanding visitors' perceptions and experiences is a prerequisite for supporting the touristic sustainability of festivals. In Turkey, no qualitative study has been found that integrates these concepts holistically and relies solely on the perspectives of festival visitors, and most of the studies conducted have been limited to quantitative methods (Çelik, 2019). Therefore, a study examining the impact of local festivals on tourism and perceptions of sustainability through visitors' experiences will fill a significant gap in both national and international literature and offer original contributions to the field of festival tourism. The lack of a visitor-focused qualitative festival sustainability research in Turkey makes this study original and important from both theoretical and practical perspectives.

This study aims to fill a significant gap in the literature by thematically analyzing the perceptions of local festival visitors. The primary objective of the study is to examine the impact of local festivals on tourism and visitor perceptions of festival sustainability from a qualitative perspective. The study attempts to understand the contributions of local festivals to tourism and their sustainability potential through the experiences, perceptions, and sustainability assessments of festival attendees.

3.2. Research Method

Qualitative research allows for the interpretation of phenomena in their natural setting and the holistic interpretation of participants' experiences. Furthermore, qualitative research offers a flexible framework for understanding individuals' lives, perceptions, and experiences in their natural settings (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2018). The phenomenological design aims to examine in depth individuals' experiences, perceptions, and the meanings they attribute to a particular phenomenon (Creswell, 2013; Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2018). Therefore, this qualitative research is based on the phenomenological design.

The semi-structured interview technique, a qualitative research technique, was used in the study. This technique allows the researcher flexibility within specific questions, allowing participants to express their opinions in detail. It also allows participants to express their thoughts in their own words and guides the interview towards specific themes (Büyüköztürk et al., 2018).

The research sample consisted of visitors residing in Silifke who had previously attended festivals. Purposive sampling was used to select participants. Purposive sampling involves selecting individuals with a wealth of information to gain an in-depth understanding of a specific phenomenon (Creswell, 2013). This method selects information-rich situations in line with the purpose of the study. Participant selection was based on the principle of voluntariness. The primary criteria for selecting participants were previous participation in festival organizations and direct participation in the festival held in Silifke. Data completeness was considered the primary factor in determining the number of participants, and a total of 16 interviews were conducted.

3.3. Development of the Data Collection Tool

Silifke was selected as a convenient sampling area, and the experiences and perceptions of individuals who attended the Silifke International Culture Festival were examined. A semi-structured interview form, developed by the researcher as a data collection tool based on similar studies in the literature, was pre-evaluated by consulting two academic experts in the field. After making necessary adjustments, the final version was finalized. In line with these criteria, face-to-face interviews were conducted with 16 visitors during the festival in Silifke between September 1 and 6, 2025. The interviews lasted an average of 25-35 minutes. To enhance the reliability of the research, the interview questions, themes, and codes were submitted to expert opinion to test their content consistency. For the ethical aspects of the research, informed verbal consent was obtained from all participants, and personal information was kept confidential.

3.4. Data Analysis

The qualitative data obtained from the study were analyzed using thematic analysis. Thematic analysis is a systematic analysis process that allows for the organization and interpretation of data by extracting meaningful patterns (themes) from participants' statements (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The analysis process includes the stages of data coding, theme generation, organization, and interpretation of themes (Miles & Huberman, 1994). In each interview, salient statements relevant to the research purpose were identified, and open codes (K1,K16) were assigned to them. The coding process was conducted independently by two researchers, and consensus was reached on the resulting themes.

4. Findings

In this section, one question was asked about festival participation, obtained from interviews with visitors, five questions about demographic characteristics of participants, four questions to determine participants' perceptions of the relationship between festivals and tourism, and three questions to determine their perceptions of the sustainability of festivals. The findings were obtained from these questions. The findings are as follows:

Participants were asked what type of festival organization they have attended before. Nine participants (K1, K2, K3, K4, K7, K8, K9, K10, K12, K13) stated that they had only attended local festivals, while seven (K5, K6, K11, K14, K15, K16) stated that they had attended both national and international festivals. In short, all participants had attended festivals before. The participants represent the sample.

Table 1. Findings regarding the demographic elements of the participants (K).

K ↓	Gender	Age	Educational (Graduation)	Status	Profession	Place of residence
K1	Male	31	Associate's degree		Cook	Silifke
K2	Female	45	Bachelor's degree		Civil Servant	Silifke
K3	Male	48	postgraduate		Academic	Mersin
K4	Female	22	High school		Intern	Silifke
K5	Male	32	High school		Cook	Mersin
K6	Male	42	High school		Cook	Mersin
K7	Female	23	Associate's degree		Receptionist	Silifke
K8	Male	46	primary school		Housekeeper	Silifke
K9	Female	27	High school		Housekeeper	Silifke
K10	Female	28	High school		İş-Kur (Workers' Union) personnel	Silifke
K11	Male	39	Bachelor's degree		Public servant	Silifke
K12	Female	24	Associate's degree		Accountant	Silifke
K13	Male	45	Bachelor's degree		Manager	Silifke
K14	Female	52	Bachelor's degree		Civil Servant	Silifke
K15	Male	49	Bachelor's degree		Music Teacher	Silifke
K16	Female	44	Bachelor's degree		Pharmacist	Silifke

According to Table 1, 8 (50%) of the participants are male and 8 (50%) are female. According to Table 1, 5 of the participants are under the age of 30, 3 are between the ages of 30-40, 7 are between the ages of 41-50, and 1 is over 50 (K14). According to Table 1, 6 of the participants have a bachelor's degree, 3 have an associate degree, 5 are high school graduates, 1 (K3) has a postgraduate degree, and 1 (K8) is a primary school graduate. While the majority of the participants live in Silifke, only 3 (K3, K5, K6) live in Mersin (3 participants are originally from Silifke and live in Mersin, but frequently come to Silifke). 3 (three) of the participants (K1, K5, K6) are cooks, while the others work in different professional groups.

Participants were asked four questions under the theme "The relationship between festivals and tourism." The findings obtained based on the answers given to the questions are as follows:

1. To the question "In your opinion, are local festivals important for tourism? In what respect do you think they are important?" all of the participants answered "they are important" while the majority of the participants answered "festivals are important for the development of tourism" (K4, K5, K6, K7, K8, K9, K10, K12, K15, K16), "they are important for attracting tourists to the region" (K1, K2, K16, K17), "they are important for the promotion of the region" (K3, K13), and K21 said they are important "for increasing entertainment opportunities in the region". Some of the answers given regarding this situation are as follows;

K1: Local festivals are important for tourism. They attract local and international tourists to the region.

K3: Yes, they are an important element in promoting a region. Festivals demonstrate a region's identity and are very effective in promoting it.

K10: Yes, they are important for tourism.

2. The participants were asked the question "Do you think that festivals increase the touristic attractiveness of the region where they are held?" The majority of the participants (K3, K4, K5, K6, K7, K8, K9, K10, K11, K12, K14, K15, K16) answered "yes, I think so", while K1 answered "I don't really think so", K2 and K13 answered "no, I don't think so" and K4 answered "I think so, it contributes to promotion". Some of the answers given regarding this situation are as follows;

K3: Yes, I think so. People visit a food production facility out of curiosity and then tell their stories back home about what they saw.

K11: Yes, I definitely think so. It helps with publicity.

K2: No, I don't. Not every festival has something that will attract tourists' attention.

3. Participants were asked, "Do you think there will be an increase in the number of tourists visiting the region during festival periods?" The majority of participants indicated that there would be an increase in the number of tourists visiting the region. Participants K4, K6, K13, and K16 responded, "Yes, it will happen," K5, K7, K8, K9, and K14 responded, "Partially it will happen," K1, K2, K10, and K11 responded, "There will be an increase in the number of domestic and foreign tourists," K13 responded, "No, it won't happen," K3 responded, "People may come for entertainment," and K15 responded, "There will be no increase in foreign tourists."

4. Participants were asked, "What do you think are the impacts of international festivals on tourism?" The majority of participants indicated that festivals have a positive impact on tourism. Participants K1, K2, K3, K10, and K14 stated that the impact of festivals on tourism is "positive," while K4, K5, K6, K7, K8, K9, K11, K15, and K16 stated that they are "positive in terms of promotion," K12 stated that they are "important economically," and K13 stated that they are "impactful at the national level." Some of the responses regarding this situation are as follows:

K2: It supports tourism by enabling the intermingling of cultures. It has a positive impact on tourism.

K5: It has a positive impact on the promotion of the region.

K9: It promotes our country and our district to different regions and has a positive impact on promotion because it creates a sense of curiosity in visitors.

The questions (3 - three questions) asked to the participants under the theme of "Sustainability of festivals" are as follows:

1. Participants were asked the question, "Do you think enough attention is paid to environmentally friendly practices during festivals?" Participants K6 and K10 stated that they "thought attention was paid to environmentally friendly practices during festivals," K7 thought "partially," and K1, K3, K11, K12, and K13 said that they "did not think attention was paid to environmentally friendly practices at local festivals." Other participants gave the following answers; "Attention is paid, but it is insufficient" (K2, K5, K14, K16), "I don't think it causes more environmental pollution" (K4), "No, I don't think enough attention is paid" (K8, K9, K15).

2. Participants were asked, "In your opinion, to what extent are festivals organized with the natural environment in mind and sustainability achieved?" All participants (100%) stated that the natural environment is not taken into account when organizing festivals. Some of the answers given to this question are as follows; "The environment is not taken into consideration during festivals" (K5, K6, K10, K11, K13, K14, K15; "little importance is given, not enough, more attention should be paid" (K7, K8, K9, K16), "festivals are not organized with the environment in mind" (K1), "not much, environmentally friendly practices should be implemented" (K2), "during festivals in general, food waste and sunflower seed shells are thrown into green areas and the environment, and the protection of the natural environment is weak" (K).

3. The question "Do you think local festivals encourage the promotion and use of local products and services?" was asked to the participants and K1, K2, K4, K5, K6, K7, K8, K9, K10, K11, K14, K15, K16 answered "yes, they encourage it", K3 answered "local products should be presented at local festivals but I do not think enough care is taken", K13 answered "normally it should encourage it but it is not at a sufficient level in our country".

5-Discussion, Conclusion And Recommendations

5.1. Discussion

The findings from the study indicate that local festivals offer significant opportunities for both tourism development and sustainability, but these opportunities are not always effectively utilized. Participant opinions revealed that festivals contribute to tourism but fall short in terms of environmental sustainability. A majority of participants emphasized that festivals play a significant role in promoting local culture and values and attracting tourists. This finding is consistent with studies in the literature that evaluate festivals as "tourist attraction elements" (Getz, 2010: 21; Derrett, 2003). It has also been noted that festivals, particularly in small-scale destinations, generate economic vitality by generating tourist flow (Yolal, Çetinel & Uysal, 2009).

Andersson & Lundberg (2013) stated in their study that considering festivals not only in economic terms but also in their social, cultural, and environmental aspects would contribute to the achievement of local development and sustainable tourism goals. Participants in the study stated that festivals lack environmentally friendly practices and that the natural environment is often overlooked. This suggests that the economic returns of festivals associated with tourism are prioritized, while sustainability principles are not sufficiently adopted.

The majority of participants stated that festivals contribute to the promotion of local products, but this contribution is often limited to short-term economic gain. This finding supports the need for festivals to be integrated with sustainable tourism. Getz and Page (2020) emphasize that festivals should include the participation of local communities and environmental protection policies in long-term tourism planning.

5.2. Conclusion

According to the research results, festivals increase the tourist appeal of destinations, contribute to the promotion of local culture and identity, and generate short-term revenue for the local economy. However, there are significant shortcomings in terms of environmental sustainability and environmental protection. Most participants stated that festivals lack sufficient attention to environmentally friendly practices and that the natural environment is overlooked. Therefore, festivals need to be restructured not only as tourist attractions but also as environmentally and socially responsible events.

Sustainably conducting festivals will contribute to both the well-being of local communities and the long-term tourism success of the destination. In this context, sustainability means not only environmental protection but also the preservation of cultural heritage and strengthening social participation.

5.3. Recommendations

Based on the research results, the following recommendations are presented:

Local governments should incorporate sustainability criteria into the festival planning process.

1. Environmental awareness-raising training and campaigns should be organized for participants, volunteers, and local residents.
2. Festivallerde yerel ürün ve hizmetlerin satışına öncelik verilerek bölgesel kalkınmaya ve ekonomik sürdürülebilirliğe katkı sağlanmalıdır.
3. Prioritizing the sale of local products and services at festivals should contribute to regional development and economic sustainability.
4. Joint research and implementation projects on sustainable event management should be conducted among universities, municipalities, and tourism stakeholders.
5. Promotion strategies should be strengthened to increase the tourism effectiveness of festivals. Efforts should be made to reach local and international potential participants, particularly through digital media, social media, and collaboration models.
6. Local governments, in particular, should integrate environmental, tourism, and cultural policies to ensure that festivals align with sustainability goals.
7. The content and nature of festivals should be carefully planned. Unique programs that combine elements of local culture, gastronomy, art, and entertainment increase visitor interest.
8. During festival periods, tourist infrastructure (transportation, accommodation, and guidance services) should be planned in advance, and investments should be made to enhance the accessibility of the festival area and ensure visitor satisfaction.
9. International collaborations and partnerships should be developed for festivals that aim to present internationally. Collaborations with foreign artists, cultural institutions, and tourism organizations increase the festival's visibility and impact.
10. Local community participation and social impact should be considered for the sustainability of festivals.
11. Recyclable materials, energy-efficient systems, and water-saving practices should be used in festival areas.

REFERENCES

Alaeddinoğlu, F. (2007). Turizmin yerel halk üzerine etkileri: Van ili örneği. *Anatolia: Turizm Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 18(1), 21-34.

Andersson, T. D., & Getz, D. (2008). Stakeholder management strategies of festivals. *Journal of Convention & Event Tourism*, 9(3), 199-220.

Andersson, T. D., & Lundberg, E. (2013). Commensurability and sustainability: Triple impact assessments of a tourism event. *Tourism Management*, 37, 68-75.

Arcodia, C., & Whitford, M. (2006). Festival attendance and the development of social capital. *Convention & Event Management*, 10(1), 1-11.

Baker, D. A., & Crompton, J. L. (2000). Quality, satisfaction and behavioral intentions. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 27(3), 785-804.

Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77-101.

Büyüköztürk, Ş., Kılış, Çakmak, E., Akgün, Ö.E., Karadeniz, Ş., & Demirel, F. (2018). *Bilimsel Araştırma Yöntemleri*, Ankara: Pegem Akademi. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/335928324_Bilimsel_Arastirma_Yontemleri/link/5d8493dea6fdce8fd6fb2ff8/download?_tp=eyJjb250ZXh0Ijp7ImZpcnN0UGFnZSI6Il9kaXJlY3QiLCJwYWdlIjoicHVibGljYXRpb24ifX0

- Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Qualitative Inquiry And Research Design: Choosing Among Five Approaches* (3rd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE. www.books.google.com.tr/books?id=Ykruxor10cYC&pg=PA1&hl=tr&source=gbs_toc_r&cad=2#v=onepage&q&f=false
- Çelik, H. (2019). Türkiye’de yerel festivallerin turizm üzerindeki etkileri: Kavramsal bir değerlendirme. *Turizm Akademik Dergisi*, 6(1), 35-48.
- Çelik, S. (2018). Festivallerin destinasyon imajı üzerindeki etkisi: Alaçatı Ot Festivali örneği. *Turizm Akademik Dergisi*, 5(2), 63-75.
- Demir, M., & Kozak, M. (2019). Festivallerin sürdürülebilir turizm açısından değerlendirilmesi. *Anatolia: Turizm Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 30(2), 45-59.
- Derrett, R. (2003). Making sense of how festivals demonstrate a community’s sense of place. *Event Management*, 8(1), 49-58.
- Getz, D. (2010). The nature and scope of festival studies. *International Journal of Event Management Research*, 5(1), 1-47.
- Getz, D., & Page, S. J. (2020). *Event Studies: Theory, Research And Policy For Planned Events* (4th ed.). London: Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315708027>
- Getz, D. (2009). Policy for sustainable and responsible festivals and events: Institutionalization of a new paradigm. *Journal of Policy Research in Tourism, Leisure and Events*, 1(1), 61-78.
- Giritlioğlu, İ., & Avcıkurt, C. (2010). Festivallerin turizme etkisi üzerine bir değerlendirme. *Anadolu Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 10(1), 99-118.
- Gursoy, D., Kim, K., & Uysal, M. (2004). Perceived impacts of festivals and special events by organizers: An extension and validation. *Tourism Management*, 25(2), 171-181.
- Hall, C. M. (2008). *Tourism planning: Policies, processes and relationships* (2nd ed.). Harlow: Pearson Education. Isbn: 0132046520, 9780132046527
- Janiskee, R. (1994). Some macroscale growth trends in America’s community festival industry. *Festival Management & Event Tourism*, 2(1), 10-14.
- Kaya, B. (2024). Silifke’de Festival Coşkusu. <https://www.mersinhaberci.com/haber/53939/silifkede-festival-coskusu.html>
- Kim, K., Uysal, M., & Chen, J. S. (2002). Festival visitor motivation from the organizers' points of view. *Event Management*, 7(2), 127-134.
- Küçükaltan, D., & Pirnar, I. (2016). Sustainable event tourism: A conceptual model. *Journal of Tourismology*, 2(1), 25-40.
- Laing, J., & Frost, W. (2010). How green was my festival: Exploring challenges and opportunities associated with staging green events. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 29(2), 261-267.
- Lee, C. K., Lee, Y. K., & Wicks, B. (2004). Segmentation of festival motivation by nationality and satisfaction. *Tourism Management*, 25(1), 61-70.
- Mair, J., & Whitford, M. (2013). An exploration of events research: Event topics, themes and emerging trends. *International Journal of Event and Festival Management*, 4(1), 6-30.
- Picard, M., & Robinson, M. (2006). *Festivals, tourism and social change: Remaking worlds*. Clevedon: Channel View Publications. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/292245158_Festivals_tourism_and_social_change_Remaking_worlds
- Richards, G., & Palmer, R. (2010). *Eventful cities: Cultural management and urban revitalisation*. Oxford: Butterworth-Heinemann. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/254786282_Eventful_Cities_Cultural_Management_and_Urban_Revitalisation/link/5ba0a1a892851ca9ed11cd3d/download?_tp=eyJjb250ZXh0Ijp7ImZpcnN0UGFnZSI6InB1YmxpY2F0aW9uIiwicGFnZSI6InB1YmxpY2F0aW9uIn19

Uzal, T.N. (2025). Sürdürülebilir Turizm Nedir? İlkeleri Nelerdir? <https://www.turizmaktuel.com/haber/surdurulebilir-turizm-nedir-ilkeleri-nelerdir?>

Yıldırım, A., & Şimşek, H. (2018). Sosyal Bilimlerde Nitel Araştırma Yöntemleri (11. baskı). Ankara: Seçkin Yayıncılık.

Yolal, M., Çetinel, F., & Uysal, M. (2009). An examination of festival motivation and perceived benefits relationship: Eskişehir International Festival. *Journal of Convention & Event Tourism*, 10(4), 276–291.